

The role of vehicular applications in the design of future 6G infrastructures

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Abstract

A great lack of 5G design is the traditional bottom-up development of network evolution, which has not effectively considered the requirements of applications and, particularly, vehicle to everything (V2X) applications. This paper provides a service-centric approach towards 6G V2X, with a concise overview of the upcoming hyper-connected vehicular ecosystem and its integration in the whole 6G fabric, analysing its particular infrastructure needs, as a way to reach key performance indicators (KPIs). We also present a 6G-oriented platform design able to manage the life-cycle of V2X applications across different domains by means of intelligent orchestration decisions.

Keywords: 6G; Vehicular communications; V2X; Applications

1. Introduction

5G is currently paving the way for reaching a hyper-connected society. However, this is still far from being truly achieved, even though the 5G standardisation process is mature enough and the first functional deployments are already running for a couple of years. In this line, it is not clear that the envisioned 5G Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), e.g., latency below 1 ms or bandwidth in the order of Gbps, are to be exploited by real applications in the short term. A possible

reason for this issue is the network-centric approach adopted when designing the 5G architecture and its related technologies. Last 3GPP releases (rel. 15–16) have mainly focused on improvements in the radio segment, laying the foundations of the 5G New Radio (5G-NR) technology. In fact, under the premise of giving generic support to enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC), and massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC) services, there was a lack of concretion regarding what are the real requirements of specific applications, until the recent appearance of 3GPP rel. 16, which details use cases and expected performances. In 6G, it is necessary to consider human-centric services [1] and, as such, the adoption of a service-centric perspective from the very beginning leads to concrete measures and efforts to design infrastructures aligned

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with the functional needs of the applications working on their top [2].

Definitely, the design and development of 6G should be also driven by a top-down approach from the first stages, considering the demands of a plethora of services that are currently waiting for a network infrastructure capable of supporting them. Although 6G aims at holistically covering a wide range of vertical sectors, there is a need for increased specificity in its design, which only can be achieved by focusing on specific verticals and their requirements. Following this rationale, from our standpoint, this is the case of vehicular services, which demand stringent requirements from a Quality of Service (QoS) perspective to the supporting network infrastructure, due to their inherent mobility and critical bandwidth, latency, and reliability requirements [3]. The importance of the Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) vertical in the 6G ecosystem is evidenced by the attention received in the 3GPP standards. In [4], the V2X architectural reference model is detailed on the basis of PC5 (Vehicle-to-Vehicle — V2V) and Uu (Vehicle-to-Infrastructure — V2I). This Technical Specification considers an Application Function (AF)-based service parameter provisioning for V2X communications, being the Network Exposure Function (NEF) component the entry-point to the core network. Through this function, the 6G application can request information about the network operation from the User Equipment (UE), apply policies, receive notifications about location changes, or request traffic routing modifications, as defined in [5,6]. This is of prominent importance to ensure compliance with QoS and security needs within this vertical, although the enabling mechanisms and its design implications are not totally defined yet.

In this line, it is essential the development of holistic infrastructures that could provide flexible deployment of 6G applications along the fog–edge–cloud continuum, at the time of ensuring high network elasticity. As discussed in next sections, this is something that has been partially investigated in 5G from the network viewpoint, but there is still a lack of platforms in the literature encompassing the 6G ecosystem and, specifically, under the umbrella of the vehicular vertical. Besides key enabling technologies for 6G, e.g., THz communications, massive MIMO, ubiquitous Artificial Intelligence (AI), etc. [7], reliable and efficient orchestration platforms for coping with QoS needs of users and applications considering the different domains of a 6G system should be further designed and developed.

1.1. Contribution

Given that 6G is currently a hot topic in the literature, different survey works have recently discussed its development path [7–19]. These works provide extensive reviews regarding 6G enabling technologies, enabled applications and services, as well as the high-level requirements to successfully support them. In general, most of these works adopt a generalist approach, trying to cover different aspects related to transit from 5G to 6G networks. However, without loss of generality, essential procedures in 6G related to perception,

communication and computation can be directly mapped into the various kinds of applications that will conform the future vehicular domain. Therefore, differently from previous 6G-related works, this paper analyses the importance of future applications, with special focus on the vehicular ones, for an effective development of 6G infrastructures. Concretely, we review the landscape of vehicular applications requiring state-of-the-art communication capabilities, from the evolutionary ones (starting from a 5G basis) to disruptive ideas that will rely on novel 6G advances.

Besides, it is crucial to comprehensively identify the main requirements of these applications and services, because they should fuel the next steps for the design of 6G systems, as mentioned above. Although some preliminary efforts have been done in previous works [10,17,18,20], further concretion is still needed to obtain objective and measurable metrics to be accomplished by next-to-come 6G infrastructures. Furthermore, given this service-centric approach, which has not been found in the literature, it is imperative the design and implementation of holistic management platforms to efficiently handle 6G-powered applications as well as their running environments and their associated resources (both physical and virtualized). This important aspect has been barely investigated either [9].

Therefore, the main contributions of this work are the following: (i) a description of the main requirements that vehicular applications will pose to the 6G infrastructure from a qualitative viewpoint; (ii) a set of heterogeneous and measurable KPIs associated with such requirements; and (iii) a functional platform that sets the foundations to cover these future needs, currently powered with features to manage and monitor 6G applications' life-cycle. Table 1 presents a comparison among the contributions of this work and those of related papers cited above.

The rest of the document is organised as follows. Section 2 explores future V2X applications enabled by 6G. Critical performance requirements of these applications are identified in Section 3, which also presents a set of KPIs related to these requirements. Section 4 describes an holistic management platform to host and support 6G applications. The paper is concluded in Section 5, which summarises the most important contributions and present future research lines.

2. V2X applications

Undergoing 6G designs will involve not only ground network deployments, but integrated architectures interconnecting space, air, ground and sea, providing 3D coverage involving space, time, and frequency domains, which will be exploited in all transport means [21]. Advances such as tactile communications, quantum computing, Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT), THz communications, Machine Learning (ML)-based network resiliency and slicing, multiple radio access technologies, intelligent reflecting surfaces, or the integration of cloud–edge–fog, will be part of the future V2X ecosystem [22]. V2X involves communications among vehicles (V2V), with infrastructure elements (V2I), with remote entities (e.g., cloud

Table 1
Comparison with previous works.

Reference	Enabled services	Enabling technologies	Service-centric perspective	Performance requirements	Identified KPIs	Specific vertical	Proposed platform
[7]	✓	✓		✓			
[8]	✓	✓					
[9]	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓
[10]	✓	✓		✓	✓		
[11]	✓	✓		✓			
[12]	✓	✓		✓	✓		
[13]		✓		✓	✓		
[14]	✓	✓		✓			
[15]	✓	✓		✓		✓	
[16]	✓	✓		✓	✓		
[17]	✓	✓		✓	✓		
[18]	✓	✓		✓	✓		
[19]	✓	✓				✓	
This work	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Fig. 1. Evolutionary 6G vehicular applications.

servers), and even with pedestrian (Vehicle-to-Pedestrian — V2P). This way, current use cases identified for Cellular V2X (C-V2X) in [23], i.e., remote driving, advanced driving, vehicle platooning, extended sensors, and vehicle QoS support, will be extended to enable more advanced features for each of these groups as well as other revolutionary applications exploiting expected 6G performances. The list of potential V2X services to be developed thanks to 6G advances is continuously increasing [21,24,25]. Evolutionary 6G applications considering already in-mind services using 5G are depicted in Fig. 1 and include:

- **Autonomous driving up to level 5.** According to SAE taxonomy [26], this involves autonomous driving with no human intervention. Especial emphasis will be put on last-mile (domestic) transportation.
Current status: Integration of 5G communications and involved technologies for enabling cooperative perception is a reality in autonomous vehicles, as recent studies indicate [27,28]. Although mass-market deployment is pending, the potential of base 5G-NR has been tested on real roads within the frame of different research

projects [29]. These works indicate that communications will be essential to complement data coming from on-board sensors, such as cameras or laser and ultrasound radars.

- **Enhanced navigation.** Thanks to improvements expected in the radio access level and drone/satellite support, positioning of sub-meter accuracy is expected, as well as extra bandwidth and network availability to receive digital maps and real-time traffic information.

Current status: The role of accurate 5G positioning is clear in the literature [30]. Improved capabilities, as compared to regular GPS, can enhance perception, decision making and control in the vehicular domain. Recent studies indicate real performances at the centimetre level [31], enabling real identification of vehicle paths within the road lane, for instance.

- **Environmental perception.** Ubiquitous network access will help vehicles exchange perception data detected by themselves and by especial hardware such as drones or static high-resolution equipment forming part of the vehicular fixed infrastructure.

Current status: The work in [32] shows a clear example on how 5G connectivity support data exchange to create a collaborative map to support navigation. In [33], the authors propose using 5G advances to speed-up an ML-based perception scheme by assuring efficient message passing. A more common scenario is exploited in [34] for enabling autonomous management of a road intersection, in this case enhanced by communications in the millimetre-wave bands of 5G.

- **In-vehicle entertainment.** Enhanced Ultra Mobile Broadband (eUMBB) and massive connectivity will enable true bidirectional 4 K/8K multimedia streams as well as truly immersing applications leveraging the advances brought by the tactile Internet and five-sense communications.

Current status: User experience will improve greatly with the integration of more efficient communications, as it is the case of the car cockpit, offering more accurate views of maps, instantaneous user assistance or access to multimedia content [35]. Live video is a common use case for evaluating data rate, given high throughput demands, but 5G technologies such as radio improvements and MEC have demonstrated to support multimedia streams efficiently under real settings [36].

- **Extended emergency services.** Aiming at further extending safe driving, Massive Ultra-Reliable and Low Latency communications (mURLL) and ultra massive Machine Type Communications (umMTC) will be supported by Visible Light Communications (VLC) and other transmission technologies, including solutions currently devoted to Internet of Things (IoT) scenarios, e.g., Low Power Wide Area Network (LPWAN). Furthermore, DLT-based solutions and quantum security will assure cybersecurity in the long term.

Current status: The integration of QoS assurance mechanisms in 5G has been exploited, for instance, to guarantee network access at emergency situations, as explained in [37]. The regular eCall services will be also subject to improvements with 5G, as proposed in [38], with a smart-phone-based accident notification service that can work at particular locations with ad-hoc network infrastructures such as tunnels.

- **Connectivity of personal mobility vehicles.** A reduction in the energy impact per bit transmitted will enable the connection of personal vehicles such as bikes or scooters using 3GPP technologies, which traditionally involve higher power consumption than LPWAN counterparts.

Current status: Given the popularity of eco-efficient personal vehicles, their integration within the C-ITS ecosystem is attracting great attention from the research community. Current efforts focus on the development of efficient and light OBUs [39] that could provide extra services to riders [40]. To this end, there are key enabling technologies from both communication and computation perspectives. Considering the former, as mentioned previously, current LPWAN solutions, e.g., LoRaWAN, Sigfox, NB-IoT, etc., are considered as the

most suitable alternatives given their long transmission distances and limited energy consumption. However, the arrival of efficient 6G transmission schemes will allow the connectivity of IoT devices in a long-term basis [41]. Regarding on-board computation, algorithms based on the TinyML paradigm can provide intelligent data-processing and decision-making with low computational overhead [42]. Other proposals adopt paradigms such as fog computing [43], computation offloading [44], or Federated Learning (FL) [45] to distribute computing-intensive tasks and alleviate energy consumption.

- **Green traffic management.** Massive equipment of connected devices will improve On-Board Unit (OBU) penetration rates, making real-time traffic management a reality and embracing scenarios such as efficient platooning, adaptive traffic lights, pollution control, on-demand green and speedy routes or emergency tracks.

Current status: Advances in platooning are a good example of exploiting 5G PC5 capabilities. In [46], the authors study this potential to create high-density platoons, taking advantage of 5G for positioning, low-latency communications and reliable connections to save fuel and reduce pollution. Emergency warning and collision avoidance services are implemented in [47], by using V2I and PC5 communications, showing the flexibility of 5G when different communication patterns are needed.

Moreover, the arrival of 6G will enable other disruptive services, thanks to radical improvements in networking and processing performance, technology penetration and consequent electronic advances. Some of these applications will be:

- **Health monitoring.** Massive connectivity and fast data processing will allow driver and passenger monitoring using connected wearable devices and in-vehicle real-time video analysis.

Current status: Driver behaviour and health monitoring is being intensively tackled by the research community [48]. Until the arrival of the autonomous vehicle, this is of prominent importance to prevent accidents, provide recommendations to the driver, or even trigger alarm messages to emergency services if an abnormal situation is detected [49]. For this analysis, multiple on-board data sources can be employed, e.g., cameras, built-in sensors such as GPS, microphone, accelerometer, gyroscope, etc. The data processing and decision making can be performed locally, for example by exploiting the TinyML paradigm [50], or offloading these tasks adopting fog or edge-computing strategies [51].

- **Augmented/mixed/virtual Reality (XR) for ground and flying vehicles.** This feature will require real-time 8 K video, timely actions, and ultra-fast update of virtual environments. Remote driving, see through or on-board panels will be real use cases integrating these advances. **Current status:** Massive extended reality and virtual reality, together with the autonomous vehicle challenge, are widely discussed in [52], indicating that involved

network requirements could be covered by future 6G networks. Virtual reality is implemented with digital twins to monitor and control drones in [53], requiring tactile Internet performances only achievable with the arrival of 6G, as it is also detailed in [54].

- **Holographic services.** mURLL and THz connectivity will allow real-time control of vehicles through remote driving by means of holograms and 3D environments as well as the development of in-vehicle holographic-powered applications.

Current status: Nowadays, we already have 2D windshield displays that improve the information provided to the driver. However, the development of these systems towards full XR-based 3D solutions is a hot research topic [55]. This will allow to show advanced visual information on the road within the driver's gaze. The advances in this regard focus on improving the information presentation to the driver [56] in order to avoid obstructions in his/her line of sight, as the impact of this type of systems on the driver is being investigated. From another perspective, holograms are being also employed for developing immersing control systems for traffic management [57] and traffic signalling [58].

- **Brain-vehicle interface.** 6G will allow wireless brain-computer interactions, requiring throughput in the order of Gbps, which could have great impact on driving interfaces for disabled people, for instance.

Current status: This area is briefly cited in previous survey works [11,22]. While presenting an innovative concept, brain-based control of vehicles is considered as a potential case of study for 6G in [59], as a way to combine neurosciences and 6G advances.

- **Wireless energy transference.** Emerging electric vehicles will be able to charge batteries wirelessly using novel energy transference schemes. This will reduce plug needs and support on-route charging using especial road infrastructure or cooperative charging with other vehicles or roadside units, thanks to a precise coordination scheme supported by the 6G infrastructure. This will also allow always-on vehicles at the time of avoiding energy-issues that may harm communication activities.

Current status: Different techniques are being proposed adopting two different approaches, namely, stationary and dynamic wireless charging. While the former is currently feasible and different wireless charging stations are available in the market [60], achieving dynamic wireless power transfer is highly challenging. Although some alternatives can be found in the literature proposing semi-dynamic [61] or fully-dynamic V2V [62] solutions, further advances are needed to achieve fully functional systems [63,64].

These are exploratory services envisaged for future 6G architectures, but their efficient and real implementation require an analysis of their particular performance requirements, in order to accurately identify the 6G technologies to be put

in place. Moreover, a comprehensive management of applications/services life-cycle will be needed across the network hierarchy, from edge nodes (e.g., OBU) to cloud infrastructure, including fog ecosystems.

3. Performance requirements

As introduced previously, it is crucial to anticipate the principal operative requirements that the range of novel applications to come in the 6G era will pose to the supporting network infrastructure. Although there is no standard definition of what a network application is in the context of the 6G ecosystem, it can be considered as a determined set of coordinated services that provide functionalities to one or multiple verticals and their associated use cases. These services are the ones that will establish the performance requirements that the 6G infrastructure will have to cope with. In the following, we present and discuss on the future challenges brought by the V2X applications identified above which, in turn, can be translated to future KPIs for 6G networks. These performance requirements are depicted in Fig. 2, indicating they are the basis over which a set of KPIs are identified in the next section.

1. **Deterministic and anticipated end-to-end QoS.** This requirement is central for ensuring applications' performance and continuity. Although some steps have been taken in 5G towards the development of effective methods for resource reservation and handling, e.g., network slicing techniques, there is still much work to do in this field in frames of 6G [65]. Firstly, it is needed to achieve a truly end-to-end resource guarantee in multi-stakeholder architectures, such as the 6G one. All the QoS actions made in a given domain should have an adequate correspondence in the subsequent ones to avoid bottle necks. Nevertheless, the diversity of technologies and management approaches in each segment notably hinder this task. Although current QoS mechanisms will continue evolving to achieve this goal, there is another challenge far to be accomplished by today: QoS anticipation. Make predictions about the future status of assigned resources and the applications working over them is a current hot topic of research. Most of the approaches leverage on AI-based mechanisms to predict future events that could impact on infrastructure performance and, consequently, on the QoS provided to applications. AI techniques are also being used to anticipate the best data path in the network in the ever-changing vehicular networks, enhancing the packet delivery ratio and reducing the end-to-end latency [66,67]. Given the characteristics of the vehicular ecosystem, e.g., high mobility, involvement of users' safety, etc., the performance and continuity of critical applications should be thoroughly guaranteed. The 6G infrastructure and its components should be designed considering this premise from the very beginning, or operational limitations could appear in subsequent development stages as it has occurred with 5G.

Fig. 2. Performance requirements identified for future V2X 6G applications and their consideration to extract relevant KPIs.

2. **Different access technologies for different application needs.** Having an enlarged and seamless coverage is of prominent importance to support next-generation applications in diverse vehicular scenarios. It is important to consider the convenience of having different-nature radio access technologies, not just those oriented to provide ultra-high data-rates, but also others than may serve as emergency links in faraway areas, e.g., LPWAN. In this case, the role of AI mechanisms is many-fold. Aligned with the previously discussed point, firstly, it is necessary an accurate and anticipated estimation of needed physical radio resources under specific channel conditions, to select the most adequate transmission technology to cope with the requirements of the working applications. Besides, given the multiple available radio access options and their flexibility, especially in urban settings, AI mechanisms can also help on the coding, waveform, modulation, and radio interface selection at the time of considering the access issues that will appear in ultra-dense scenarios. The main challenge here is the dynamic and changing nature of the physical radio media and terminals, which may hinder the generation of datasets capable of covering many different scenarios and situations. Reinforcement Learning (RL) may give answer to this issue [68], but more efforts are needed in this regard. Furthermore, the massive presence of connected devices leads to a saturated radio medium; thus, its precise and adequate management in real-time becomes of remarked relevance.
3. **AI-powered network orchestration and reprogrammability.** Resource allocation from a networking perspective has been addressed from many years ago, but it has gained momentum lately under the umbrella of

the 5G network slicing concept. Thanks to already well-known technologies such as Software Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualisation (NFV), complex network architectures are becoming adaptable to real-time application requirements. However, there is still a long way to achieve well-orchestrated systems, especially in disaggregated multi-provider and multi-vendor architectures such as those envisioned for 6G [69]. Therefore, there is a lack of end-to-end orchestrators coordinating available resources in the different network segments, e.g., Radio Access Network (RAN), edge, transport, core, etc. This will be even more exacerbated in architectures where different stakeholders will manage and exploit individual 6G domains. Current research efforts are devoted to the development of holistic AI-powered orchestration and decision-making engines able to monitor the status of the whole infrastructure to provide accurate and flexible resource-management plans [70]. In this line, the intent-based network management paradigm is gaining great relevance. It permits network administrators to define outcomes or operative objectives and the system figures out how to achieve that goal in an autonomous way, thus following a Zero-touch Service Management (ZSM) approach.

4. **AI-based application life-cycle management.** Current 5G features already supporting traffic management and new virtualisation environments, such as Kubernetes, have evolved to support the migration of computing units, i.e., Virtual Network Functions (VNFs). However, there is further work needed to guarantee a seamless transition of network and computing resources following vertical (through the network hierarchy) and horizontal (e.g., following the vehicle route) paths [71].

V2X applications will require stringent requirements to be fulfilled on mobility; hence, operation of virtualisation and SDN technologies should be accompanied by continuous monitoring and anticipation of QoS to feed AI/ML-based on-line resource planning algorithms. Furthermore, traditional hierarchical orchestration should also consider peer-to-peer scenarios in which computing units or domains exchange application needs and available resources, to finally decide application placement. This could be the key for decoupling from computing resources exclusively offered from major and dominant cloud and network operators, and then open the door for enthusiasts and small/medium organisations to play the game of cloud/edge computing in 6G.

5. **Multi-domain secure and reliable application onboarding environments.** The inherent nature of mobile services implies physical movements which lead to constant domain changes that result in multiple challenges to be tackled. Therefore, the infrastructure supporting the onboarding and deployment of this new generation of network applications will require environments capable of handling multiple domains [72]. The coordination among them becomes a critical aspect for the management system, in order to handle the handovers and minimise the impact in service provisioning. Entities with global vision of the network or federated collaborative hierarchies may be valid approaches to manage domain heterogeneity. Besides, the onboarding environments should make available the deployment of applications in different points of the multi-domain architecture, which undoubtedly arises security, privacy, and reliability concerns. Software artefacts composing applications become in this paradigm sensitive assets where special attention must be paid. Solutions that assure integrity of these artefacts during the onboarding and, mainly, during the deployment across multiple domains will be imperative. Furthermore, special care should be given to the confidentiality considerations for the distributed storage of the artefacts across the value chain. Finally, the placement process of a given application in a certain domain should include exploratory performance tests for ensuring that its QoS requirements are being met.
6. **Multi-dimension perception and accurate positioning at high-speeds.** Besides the extended range of on-board sensors that will permit to enhance vehicle's environmental perception, future applications will require gathering sensed data from peripheral sources, e.g., other vehicles, road infrastructure, pedestrians, etc. Depending on the service, stringent latency constraints may appear (near real-time information exchange) [73] as well as issues related to data validity, caching, and freshness, as discussed in the following point. To deal with these aspects, edge computing will play a relevant role given its computation, data aggregation, and low-latency capabilities. Regarding accurate positioning, next-gen apps will require centimetre-level precision to support services like autonomous or advanced

driving. In this case, 6G infrastructures should provide this positioning accuracy in a fast and reliable manner [74], given that current satellite-based technologies could not guarantee such performance. All these tasks, together with general communication activities, should be supported at end-device's super high speeds, to cover the different transportation means under consideration, including flying objects or high-speed trains.

7. **Data caching and data freshness.** The Internet, mobile services and, lately, cloud services have popularised immediacy access to data in a permanently information world. However, data-retrieving latency in 6G must be much lower than in 5G [75]. This will be achieved by taking the requested resource closer to the user, making it easier to be found, for instance by adopting an edge-computing approach, as previously discussed. In this line, the Content Delivery Network (CDN) scheme needs to evolve to systems in which information and location are completely decoupled, similarly to Information-Centric Networking (ICN) solutions, therefore allowing network-aware AI-based data distribution [76]. This approach introduces two main challenges: first, management of data access and privacy needs to be enforced by the network itself, as further developed in the next point; and, second, encrypted communications and dynamic content in multi-stakeholder scenarios complicate the inspection of information identifiers, such as URLs, and the freshness of generated responses. Systems to decide and probably guess in real-time if a precise request should be relied to a caching system or to an edge-deployed service need to be developed and integrated. Even if access to information is the key objective of the network, to achieve this objective, the decision-making elements of 6G network orchestration need to be fed with immediate control and sensing data. These AI-powered elements have transited from a centralised management, to a distributed arrangement and, therefore, they need rapid and trustworthy access to signalling and control data similarly to how it is done for customer traffic.
8. **Data trust, security, and privacy.** Cybersecurity in every aspect is of outstanding relevance in vehicular scenarios as the safety of the vehicle's occupants may be compromised. The number of potential attacks is huge in this context; hence, protecting sensitive data is pivotal to ensure proper operation of applications. However, the convergence of diverse connectivity options into a common architecture is highly challenging from a cybersecurity perspective. Given the diverse nature of available radio access technologies, future 6G specifications should firmly set the security policies that each one should comply with in order to gain access to the 6G infrastructure [77]. This foundational aspect, specific cybersecurity assets for each architecture domain should be developed and AI-based orchestrated, to ensure the overall system stability and integrity of on-board equipment in vehicular domains [78]. As mentioned previously, the multi-vendor/provider nature of

6G architectures calls for joint efforts that enable holistic cyber-defence to ensure data, user and infrastructure components security, privacy, and trust. In this case, the use of DLT-based trustworthy management platforms may permit to handle these sensitive data, preserving their privacy at the time of putting them at disposal of all the involved stakeholders. Another key technology in this regard is Federated Learning (FL). This paradigm proposes the distributed training of a common model, e.g., an anomaly or attack detector, in order to increase its robustness while ensuring the privacy of the training data [79]. Following this strategy, the obtained model gathers the different knowledge contributed by participants, hence permitting one element, e.g., a given vehicle, to be protected from attacks never seen before by itself, but reported by other collaborators. Finally, given the prominent role of AI in the decision-making processes along the end-to-end 6G segments, evaluating and scoring the trustworthiness and liability of these algorithms is of relevant importance. Consequently, the further development of the explainable-AI paradigm should be a reality in order to be considered from the first stages of the 6G ecosystem design.

9. **Energy efficiency.** Given intense communication activities required by upcoming applications, data transmission and processing tasks should increase their efficiency in comparison with current 5G power consumption in both end-devices and the infrastructure [80]. Regarding the former, energy efficiency is highly related to the Quality of Experience (QoE) provided to the users, as they expect long battery working periods without the need of charging their devices. Besides, reducing the energy consumed by the overall infrastructure is crucial for sustainability and economic reasons. Therefore, current techniques such as energy harvesting, sleeping periods or energy-aware offloading need to be further developed to reduce the energy footprint of the overall 6G system.

Besides the qualitative requirements identified so far, it is also necessary the identification of specific and measurable KPIs that can reflect the performance reached by the network infrastructure in different planes. Table 2 presents a non-exhaustive list of KPIs that will be fundamental for enabling an effective support of next-gen vehicular applications by 6G infrastructures. As can be seen, each KPI in the table is linked to the requirements discussed above, and they are classified into four groups, that belong to different abstraction layers, namely, user equipment (UE) and infrastructure hardware, RAN, network, and application, as well as two transversal groups: AI and security.

4. 6G network infrastructure to manage V2X applications life-cycle

Holistic management solutions will be of utmost importance to effectively host and support upcoming 6G applications. In this section, we present a functional platform with

the potential to handle this kind of applications and the capabilities to manage and orchestrate their life-cycle within the automotive ecosystem.

Throughout the last sections, we have analysed the 6G infrastructure needs that will be claimed by upcoming vehicular applications and services. 5G architecture already includes an unprecedented level of flexibility when compared with past-generation networks. To understand how it can be further evolved, it is helpful to study existing 5G network application management platforms. Different solutions have been proposed during the last years with the aim of implementing most of 5G capabilities and going one step beyond with regard to network programmability, experimentation, and automation under the umbrella of the vehicular ecosystem. Thereby, the Federal Mobility Group's 5G and Mobile Network Infrastructure Working Group,¹ evaluated 5G testing approaches in the USA and defined a framework for federal 5G testing. This solution is built on the insights obtained from the analysis of existing cases and proposed a modular approach to support current needs and explore new and enhanced 5G capabilities. The 5GinFIRE project² developed an open and extensible 5G and NFV architecture comprised of experimental facilities to integrate existing applications and enabling the instantiation of fully-softwarised vertical infrastructures to experiment with them. The platform was showcased as an enabler to instantiate and operate vehicular solutions. Another platform was the one developed by the 5G-VINNI project³ where an E2E 5G facility was implemented to allow vertical industries to test and validate specific 5G applications. One of the future verticals targeted by the infrastructure of the project was the vehicular ecosystem, due to its stringent requirements as explained along this paper. In turn, in the 5G-EVE project,⁴ the interconnection of existing European sites located in different countries to form a single multi-domain E2E platform was carried out. This platform was designed as an experimentation workbench in which the deployed network applications could be tested over multiple domains. There are also ongoing projects that are developing platforms to manage the life-cycle of network applications within the 5G architecture. The 5GASP project⁵ aims at building an operating, open and inter-domain 5G ecosystem of experimental facilities that will permit the experimentation and validation of network applications with vertical-specific requirements. The proposal is based on a DevOps approach with an automated pipeline that deploys, tests and validates the applications and services. For demonstration purposes, 5GASP adopts vehicular and public disaster relief and recovery use cases. Finally, 5G-IANA⁶ is developing an automotive open experimental platform, coupled with a development toolkit tailored to the vehicular vertical. The aim of this initiative is to make easier the development, instantiation and testing of 5G vehicular applications.

¹ <https://www.cio.gov>

² <https://5ginfire.eu>

³ <https://www.5g-vinni.eu>

⁴ <https://www.5g-eve.eu>

⁵ <https://www.5gasp.eu>

⁶ <https://www.5g-iana.eu>

Table 2

Set of KPIs related to the identified 6G-app's requirements.

Category	KPI	Description	Requirements
Hardware	Infrastructure energy consumption (W)	Energy consumption of fixed infrastructure	9
	UE energy consumption (W)	Energy consumption of terminals	9
	Watt usage estimation (W)	Estimation of the watts amount consumed by V/PNF used by the network to provide the service	9
RAN	Bandwidth per terminal (bps)	Available bandwidth per terminal in both downlink and uplink	1, 2
	Signal strength (e.g., RSSI - dBm)	Signal level received by the terminal	2
	Signal quality (e.g., SNR - dB)	Signal over background noise at the terminal	2
	Handover reliability (%)	Ratio of successfully completed handover events within the RAN	2, 3, 5
	Mobility interruption time (μ s)	Time a user terminal loses connectivity during handovers	2, 3, 5
	Mobility/speed (m/s)	Maximum device's speed supported without hindering the communication link	2, 6
	Spectral efficiency (bps/Hz)	Data rate per spectral bandwidth unit	2
	Spectrum (Hz)	Available bandwidth per cell	1, 2
	UE density (#UE/m ²)	Number of simultaneously connected devices per area unit	2, 9
Network	Network capacity (b)	Maximum data volume transferred on a particular geographical area per time slot	1, 2, 3, 7
	Network latency (μ s)	Time since a data packet is transmitted until it is received	1, 2, 3, 4, 7
	Network jitter (μ s)	Fluctuation in the network latency	1, 2, 3, 4, 7
	Network management response time (μ s)	Time from event detection to effective reaction in the management of the network, taking into account analysis and decision making	1, 3, 4, 8
	Network reliability (%)	Amount of application/network layer packet successfully delivered	1, 2, 3
	Network throughput (bps)	Instantaneous data rate/throughput as perceived at the network layer	1, 2, 3, 4, 7
	Position accuracy (cm)	Deviation radius of measured position using terminal's 6G positioning service	1, 6
	UE connection delay (μ s)	Control plane latency in the terminal connection status to move from idle state to active state	2, 3, 4
	Slicing creation delay (μ s)	Time needed to make effective an E2E network slice	2, 3, 5
	Slicing QoS compliance (%)	Level of compliance with slicing QoS requirements indicated	3, 4, 8
	System components' trustworthiness (%)	Trust between elements within the disaggregated 6G architecture	3, 5

(continued on next page)

Our functional 6G platform proposal is based on the common experimental perspective adopted by the aforementioned solutions. This approach is essential in the design and development of new network applications, as it enables validation of correct operation of deployed services and checking compliance with QoS requirements, attending to defined KPIs. It has been proved to be a useful and efficient way to handle the lifecycle of vertical applications in complex communication architectures. Besides, the underlying approach perfectly combines with multi-domain E2E AI-powered orchestration

and continuous infrastructure monitoring, hence being potentially able to efficiently handle V2X services in future 6G infrastructures.

The proposed architecture can be seen in Fig. 3. The expected 6G multi-provider and multi-vendor scenario explained above is considered by representing two different domains in the infrastructure. The End-to-End (E2E) path is managed by the E2E Network Function Vitalisation Orchestrator (E2E NFVO), which coordinates the local NFVOs to deploy the application's components and to set up E2E network slices across

Table 2 (continued).

Category	KPI	Description	Requirements
Application	Application's handover resiliency (%)	Ratio of successfully completed handovers without service interruption	4, 5
	Bootstrapping time (μ s)	Latency in the bootstrapping of applications and their connectivity	3, 4, 5
	Cache hit ratio (%)	Rate of successful cache hit events per information requests	7
	Data population time (μ s)	Time from data request to data cached event, including cache node selection and arrangement made by network to relay the request	5, 7
	Data quality (%)	Quality of sensed and cached data	6, 7
	Data trust and reliability (%)	Trustworthiness on data employed at application level	7, 8
	Migration time (μ s)	Latency in the migration of applications between virtualized environments, including multi-domain migrations	3, 4, 5
	Service downtime (μ s)	Period of time in which the application is unresponsive, but connectivity is present	1
	Transaction rate (#transactions/s)	Rate at which database or DLT enabled applications can attend requests	1,3
AI	AI accuracy (%)	Correctness or precision of AI-based decisions in network and application management	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8
	AI decision time (μ s)	Latency for making a decision once the model is operative	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8
	AI explainability (%)	Capability to let human users comprehend and trust the results and output created by AI algorithms	3, 4
	AI training time (s)	Latency for the training stage of AI models	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8
	AI trustworthiness (%)	Trust on AI algorithms' decisions	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8
	Intelligent management liability (%)	Adjustment of AI algorithms to SLAs and laws	3, 4
Security	Confidentiality and integrity (%)	Data is not open and cannot be modified by non-authorized users	5, 8
	Privacy assurance (%)	Prevention of disclosing personal or critical information for services	3, 4, 5, 8
	Cyber-attacks prevented (#cyber-attacks)	Cyber-attacks detected and correctly prevented per time slot	5, 8
	Malicious scale-up ratio (%)	Ratio of resource reservation increases due to malicious workload	3, 9
	Security SLA infringement (#infringements)	Number of times that a security agreement is broken due to attacks or unmatched configurations per time slot	3, 5, 8
	Threat assessment (#threats)	Estimation of potential threats based on final deployment decisions, from each component involved or aggregated per time slot	3, 4, 5, 8

domains. Application components, in the form of VNFs, are deployed on top of the network slices required by the service. Network resources necessary for each slice are allocated via the Network Manager in the physical infrastructure to finally set up an E2E network slice across the different domains within the involved 6G infrastructure. These slices, together with the application's VNFs and their associated compute and storage resources, are managed thanks to the Virtual Infrastructure Managers (VIMs) within each domain. Moreover, Physical Network Functions (PNFs), involving common

network hardware not supporting vitalisation and software-based management, can also support their deployment via the Network Manager.

The E2E NFVO also interacts with the E2E Testing Manager, which orchestrates the preparation and execution of the testing plans established for the deployed applications. The aim is to evaluate the performance of a just deployed application, with specific QoS requirements, considering a certain set of selected KPIs (see Table 2). To do so, the E2E Testing Manager directly collaborates with domain Testing

Fig. 3. 6G application management architecture.

Managers to set up local Testing Agents and to coordinate the test procedure. QoS requirements for each application can be subject to Service Level Agreements (SLAs) agreed among the different domains and stakeholders involved in the disaggregated 6G deployment.

Besides, the performance of each local domain's infrastructure and instantiated functions is continuously monitored, gathering KPI measurements that are sent to the corresponding local NFVO. The intelligence of the system relies on both the E2E NFVO and the multiple NFVOs along the highly-distributed 6G architecture. They gather performance and monitoring measurements to feed intelligent components that infer the status of the E2E path and react in real-time to changes in the network, to assure the fulfilment of the application QoS requirements, e.g., by migrating a certain application from one domain or processing node to another.

The testing process is understood as a key stage during the application deployment, to ensure that its QoS requirements

are met. For this reason, in the following, the aforementioned testing process is detailed through a sequence diagram in which the interactions between the different architecture's entities can be seen and are further explained. As indicated in Fig. 4, the Service Provider is the originator of the deployment process. It is in charge of providing the application to be deployed together with the QoS requirements that need to be fulfilled (1). This entity may be played by different actors, ranging from Internet Service Provider (ISP) or Business Support Systems (BSS), to Over-The-Top (OTT) companies. Considering that the E2E NFVO approves the application deployment according to its QoS requirements and available SLAs, this entity delegates the process to local NFVOs placed at the application's geographical or administrative range (2). At that point, each NFVO will deploy the required network slice by orchestrating the corresponding Network Manager (3, 4) and VIM (5, 6), managing the physical infrastructure. As soon as the network slice is ready to host the application, the

Fig. 4. Interactions during application life-cycle.

set of VNFs composing it are deployed by the VIM and the application is considered as launched (7, 8).

At this point, it is necessary to ensure that the deployed application complies with the specified QoS. This is achieved by testing the responsiveness of the application through the E2E Testing Manager (9), which orchestrates the process using domain-specific Testing Managers (10, 14). This is carried out using test configurations pushed to a local Test Agent (11, 12), which measures the performance and operation of components instantiated in the particular domain in terms of KPIs, and generates a compliance result (15, 16). These tests can be carried out once, periodically or on-demand, depending on system configuration and application behaviour. The outcome of these validations, successful or not, is sent to the E2E NFVO and the Service Provider (18, 19). If the test results do not comply with the required levels of QoS, or some performance degradation along the end-to-end path is detected by the domain-specific monitoring services during run-time (20, 21), a reconfiguration phase may be needed. Such a process aims at rearranging the available resources in the different domains to address changes in the network that are impairing the end-to-end QoS provided by the infrastructure. This can be done by selecting a new network slice with updated network requirements or by instantiating more computing resources.

This reconfiguration is performed by the local NFVO (22–25), and it is notified to the E2E NFVO (26) to reassess the E2E compliance with QoS requirements and to the Service Provider (27). Besides, it can potentially trigger other reconfigurations in neighbouring NFVOs; hence, the performance and operation of the reconfigured application would be tested and validated as in the deployment phase (28, 29), providing its results to the E2E NFVO and to the Service Provider (30, 31).

As it can be seen through the application life-cycle, the Service Provider will be notified of relevant status changes, including the deployment success (8), application tested and running (19), and each time the application is reconfigured (27) and tested again (31). This permits smart adaptation of application behaviour according to live network evolution.

5. Conclusion

At the time that the 5G technology is being effectively implanted, current research advances are envisioning the next-generation of cellular networks, i.e., 6G. While the design and implementation of 5G has followed a bottom-up approach, the demands of futuristic applications to come should be taken as a cornerstone for the successful implementation of 6G infrastructures. In that sense, highly demanding verticals,

such as vehicular applications, will play an essential role for establishing the main performance requirements that should be guaranteed by future 6G deployments. Thus, this article has widely overviewed current and future vehicular applications as well as their principal needs. The qualitative identification of application's requirements has led to their materialisation onto measurable KPIs, which may be valuable during the design phases of the different disaggregated 6G sub-domains. Given the relevance of controlling the whole life-cycle of a given instantiated application, a 6G-oriented platform that permits to manage its deployment across different domains, as well as monitoring its QoS performance, has been presented. The proposed platform enables testing the application after its instantiation to decide whether its QoS requirements are met. Besides, this orchestration platform bets on reconfiguring network and computation virtualised infrastructures, or migrate the application on-the-fly, upon the detection of a performance decrease. Future research lines include the detailed evaluation of this solution under network and computing-stressing vehicular scenarios involving autonomous driving conditions as a next step in our activities within the 5GASP European project and the R3CAV and Cerberus national initiatives.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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